

Resourceful Program Synthesis from Graded Linear Types (Appendix)

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This document contains the supplementary material for the paper of the same name which appears in the Springer LNCS proceedings for LOPSTR 2020. Included are the complete synthesis calculi and their focusing forms, the full list of benchmarks, as well as proofs for all lemmas which appear in the paper.

A Collected Rules of the Subtractive Calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma} \text{LINVAR}^- \quad \frac{\exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma, x : [A]_s} \text{GRVAR}^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad y \notin |\Delta| \quad \exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- [x/y]t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'}} \text{DER}^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^- \lambda x. t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- [(x_1 \ t_2)/x_2]t_1; \Delta_2} \text{L}\multimap^- \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^- [t]; \Gamma - r * (\Gamma - \Delta)} \text{R}\Box^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma, x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} \text{L}\Box^- \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^- \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_2} \text{R}\otimes^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta \quad x_1 \notin |\Delta| \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta} \text{L}\otimes^- \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad \Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta \quad \Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_2^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma, x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad x_3 \notin |\Delta_2|}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{case} x_1 \mathbf{of} \mathbf{inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; \Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2} \text{L}\oplus^- \\
\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^- (); \Gamma} \text{R}1^- \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} \text{L}1^-
\end{array}$$

B Collected Rules of the Additive Calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : A} \text{LINVAR}^+ \quad \frac{}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : [A]_1} \text{GRVAR}^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, y : A}{\Gamma, x : [A]_s \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ [x/y]t; \Delta + x : [A]_1} \text{DER}^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A}{\Gamma \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^+ \lambda x.t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{L}\multimap^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^+ [t]; r * \Delta} \text{R}\Box^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{if } x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta \text{ then } s \sqsubseteq r \text{ else } 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Gamma, x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; (\Delta \setminus x_2), x_1 : \Box_r A} \text{L}\Box^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} \text{R}\otimes^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B}{\Gamma, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B} \text{L}\otimes^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inl} t_1; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_1^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inr} t_2; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_2^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad \Gamma, x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{case } x_1 \mathbf{of inl } x_2 \rightarrow t_1 | \mathbf{inr } x_3 \rightarrow t_2; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B} \text{L}\oplus^+ \\
\\
\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^+ (); \emptyset} \text{R}1^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta, x : 1} \text{L}1^+
\end{array}$$

B.1 Alternative pruning rules for pair introduction and application

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{L}'\multimap^+ \\
\\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} \text{R}'\otimes^+
\end{array}$$

C List of benchmark synthesis problems

In the following $\Box A$ is shorthand for $\Box_{[0..\infty]}A$ (graded modality with indices drawn from intervals over $\mathbb{N} \cup \infty$).

Hilbert	
\otimes Intro	$\otimes_i : \forall a, b. a \multimap b \multimap (a \otimes b)$
\otimes Elim	$\otimes_{e1} : \forall a, b. (a \otimes \Box_0 b) \multimap a$ $\otimes_{e2} : \forall a, b. (\Box_0 a \otimes b) \multimap b$
\oplus Intro	$\oplus_{i1} : \forall a, b. a \multimap a \oplus b$ $\oplus_{i2} : \forall a, b. b \multimap a \oplus b$
\oplus Elim	$\oplus_e : \forall a, b, c. \Box_{[0..1]}(a \multimap c) \multimap \Box_{[0..1]}(b \multimap c) \multimap (a \oplus b) \multimap c$
SKI	$s : \forall a, b, c. (a \multimap (b \multimap c)) \multimap (a \multimap b) \multimap (\Box_2 a \multimap c)$ $k : \forall a, b. a \multimap \Box_0 b \multimap a$ $i : \forall a. a \multimap a$
Comp	
mult	$\circ : \forall a, b, c. (a \multimap b) \multimap (b \multimap c) \multimap (a \multimap c)$
0/1	$\circ_{I/O} : \forall a, b, c. \Box(\Box a \multimap \Box b) \multimap \Box(\Box b \multimap \Box c) \multimap \Box(\Box a \multimap \Box c)$
CBN	$\circ_{CBN} : \forall a, b, c. \Box(\Box a \multimap b) \multimap \Box(\Box b \multimap c) \multimap \Box a \multimap c$
CBV	$\circ_{CBV} : \forall a, b, c. \Box(\Box a \multimap \Box b) \multimap \Box(\Box b \multimap \Box c) \multimap \Box \Box a \multimap \Box c$
coK- \mathcal{R}	$\circ_{\mathcal{R}} : \forall \mathcal{R}, r, s \in \mathcal{R}, a, b, c. \Box_r(\Box_s a \multimap b) \multimap (\Box_r b \multimap c) \multimap \Box_{r*s} a \multimap c$
coK- \mathbb{N}	$\circ_{\mathbb{N}} : \forall r, s \in \mathbb{N}, a, b, c. \Box_r(\Box_s a \multimap b) \multimap (\Box_r b \multimap c) \multimap \Box_{r*s} a \multimap c$
Dist	
\oplus - \mathbb{N}	$pull_{\oplus} : \forall r : \mathbb{N}, a, b. (\Box_r a \oplus \Box_r b) \multimap \Box_r(a \oplus b)$
\oplus -!	$pull_{\oplus} : \forall a, b. (\Box a \oplus \Box b) \multimap \Box(a \oplus b)$
\oplus - \mathcal{R}	$pull_{\oplus} : \forall \mathcal{R}, r \in \mathcal{R}, a, b. (\Box_r a \oplus \Box_r b) \multimap \Box_r(a \oplus b)$
\otimes - \mathbb{N}	$pull_{\otimes} : \forall r : \mathbb{N}, a, b. (\Box_r a \otimes \Box_r b) \multimap \Box_r(a \otimes b)$
\otimes -!	$pull_{\otimes} : \forall a, b. (\Box a \otimes \Box b) \multimap \Box(a \otimes b)$
\otimes - \mathcal{R}	$pull_{\otimes} : \forall \mathcal{R}, r, a, b. (\Box_r a \otimes \Box_r b) \multimap \Box_r(a \otimes b)$
\multimap - \mathbb{N}	$push_{\multimap} : \forall r : \mathbb{N}, a, b. \Box_r(a \multimap b) \multimap \Box_r a \multimap \Box_r b$
\multimap -!	$push_{\multimap} : \forall a, b. \Box(a \multimap b) \multimap \Box a \multimap \Box b$
\multimap - \mathcal{R}	$push_{\multimap} : \forall \mathcal{R}, r : \mathcal{R}, a, b. \Box_r(a \multimap b) \multimap \Box_r a \multimap \Box_r b$
Vec	
vec5	$vmap_5 : \forall a, b. \Box_5(a \multimap b) \multimap (((a \otimes a) \otimes a) \otimes a) \otimes a$ $\multimap (((b \otimes b) \otimes b) \otimes b) \otimes b)$
vec10	$vmap_{10} : \forall a, b. \text{as above but for 10-tuples}$
vec15	$vmap_{15} : \forall a, b. \text{as above but for 15-tuples}$
vec20	$vmap_{20} : \forall a, b. \text{as above but for 20-tuples}$
Misc	
split \oplus	$split : \forall a, b, c. \Box_{[2..3]} b \multimap (a \oplus c) \multimap ((a \otimes \Box_{[2..2]} b) \oplus (c \otimes \Box_{[3..3]} b))$
split \otimes	$split : \forall a, b. \Box_{[0..2]}(a \multimap a \multimap a) \multimap \Box_{[10..10]} a \multimap (\Box_{[2..2]} a \otimes \Box_{[6..6]} a)$
share	$share : \forall a, b. \Box_4 a \multimap \Box_6 a \multimap \Box_2((((a \otimes a) \otimes a) \otimes a) \otimes a) \multimap (b \otimes b)$
Exm. 3	$noLeak : \forall a, b. (\Box_{Lo} a \otimes \Box_{Hi} a) \multimap (\Box_{Lo}(a \otimes 1) \multimap b) \multimap b$

D Focusing Forms of the Synthesis Calculi

D.1 Subtractive Resource Management

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RIGHTASYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \uparrow \Rightarrow^- \lambda x. t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^- \quad \frac{\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not right async}}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash C \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{R}\uparrow^- \\
\text{LEFTASYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta \quad x_1 \notin |\Delta| \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \text{let } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \text{ in } t_2; \Delta} \text{L}\otimes^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad x_3 \notin |\Delta_2|}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \text{case } x_2 \text{ of inl } x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mid \text{inr } x_3 \rightarrow t_2; \Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2} \text{L}\oplus^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : \square_r A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- \text{let } [x_2] = x_1 \text{ in } t; \Delta} \text{L}\square^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \text{let } () = x \text{ in } t; \Delta} \text{L}1^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; x : [A]_s, y : A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad y \notin |\Delta| \quad \exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- [x/y]t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'}} \text{DER}^- \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad A \text{ not left async}}{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{L}\uparrow^- \\
\text{FOCUS} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not atomic}}{\Gamma; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSR}^- \quad \frac{\Gamma; x : A \downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : A; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSL}^- \\
\text{RIGHTSYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash B \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \downarrow \Rightarrow^- \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_2} \text{R}\otimes^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \downarrow \Rightarrow^- \text{inr } t; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_2^- \quad \frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \downarrow \Rightarrow^- \text{inl } t; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_1^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \square_r A \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Gamma - r * (\Gamma - \Delta)} \text{R}\square^- \\
\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^- (); \Gamma} \text{R}1^- \quad \frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{R}\downarrow^- \\
\text{LEFTSYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash A \downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- [(x_1 \ t_2)/x_2]t_1; \Delta_2} \text{L}\multimap^- \\
\frac{}{\Gamma; x : A \downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma} \text{LINVAR}^- \quad \frac{\exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma, x : [A]_s} \text{GRVAR}^- \\
\frac{\Gamma; x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad A \text{ not atomic and not left sync}}{\Gamma; x : A \downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{L}\downarrow^-
\end{array}$$

D.2 Additive Resource Management

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RIGHTASYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \uparrow \Rightarrow^+ \lambda x.t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not right async}}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash C \uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta} \text{R}\uparrow^+ \\
\text{LEFTASYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B} \text{L}\otimes^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad \Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{case} x_2 \mathbf{of} \mathbf{inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B} \text{L}\oplus^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{if } x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta \text{ then } s \sqsubseteq r \text{ else } 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : \square_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; (\Delta \setminus x_2), x_1 : \square_r A} \text{L}\square^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; x : [A]_s, y : A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, y : A \quad \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : [A]_s \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ [x/y]t; \Delta + x : [A]_1} \text{DER}^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta, x : 1} \text{L}1^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad A \text{ not left async}}{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{L}\uparrow^+ \\
\text{FOCUS} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not atomic}}{\Gamma; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSR}^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : A; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSL}^+ \\
\text{RIGHTSYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} \text{R}\otimes^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_1^+ \quad \frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} \text{R}\oplus_2^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \square_r A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ [t]; r * \Delta} \text{R}\square^+ \quad \frac{}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^+ (); \emptyset} \text{R}1^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{R}\Downarrow^+ \\
\text{LEFTSYNC} \\
\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{L}\multimap^+ \\
\frac{}{\Gamma; x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : A} \text{LINVAR}^+ \quad \frac{}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : [A]_1} \text{GRVAR}^+ \\
\frac{\Gamma; x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad A \text{ not atomic and not left sync}}{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{L}\Downarrow^+
\end{array}$$

Alternative Pruning Rules for Pair Introduction and Application

$$\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{L}'_{\multimap^+}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} \text{R}'_{\otimes^+}$$

E Soundness proofs

This appendix gives the proofs of Lemma 2 and Lemma 3, along with soundness results for the variant systems: additive pruning and subtractive division.

We first state and prove some intermediate results about context manipulations which are needed for the main lemmas.

Definition 5 (Context approximation). *For contexts Γ_1, Γ_2 then:*

$$\frac{}{\emptyset \sqsubseteq \emptyset} \quad \frac{\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2}{\Gamma_1, x : A \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2, x : A}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2 \quad r \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma_1, x : [A]_r \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2, x : [A]_s} \quad \frac{\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2 \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2, x : [A]_s}$$

This is actioned in type checking by iterative application of APPROX.

Lemma 5 $(\Gamma + (\Gamma' - \Gamma'') \sqsubseteq (\Gamma + \Gamma') - \Gamma'')$.

Proof. Induction over the structure of both Γ' and Γ'' . The possible forms of Γ' and Γ'' are considered in turn:

1. $\Gamma' = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma'' = \emptyset$

We have:

$$(\Gamma + \emptyset) - \emptyset = \Gamma + (\emptyset - \emptyset)$$

From definitions 1 and 4, we know that on the left hand side:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma + \emptyset) - \emptyset &= \Gamma + \emptyset \\ &= \Gamma \end{aligned}$$

and on the right-hand side:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma + (\emptyset - \emptyset) &= \Gamma + \emptyset \\ &= \Gamma \end{aligned}$$

making both the left and right hand sides equivalent:

$$\Gamma = \Gamma$$

2. $\Gamma' = \Gamma', x : A$ and $\Gamma'' = \emptyset$

We have

$$(\Gamma + \Gamma', x : A) - \emptyset = \Gamma + (\Gamma, x : A - \emptyset)$$

From definitions 1 and 4, we know that on the left hand side we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma + \Gamma', x : A) - \emptyset &= (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A - \emptyset \\ &= (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A \end{aligned}$$

and on the right hand side:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma + (\Gamma, x : A - \emptyset) &= \Gamma + \Gamma', x : A \\ &= (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A \end{aligned}$$

making both the left and right hand sides equal:

$$(\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A = (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A$$

3. $\Gamma' = \Gamma', x : A$ and $\Gamma'' = \Gamma'', x : A$

We have

$$(\Gamma + \Gamma', x : A) - \Gamma'', x : A = \Gamma + (\Gamma', x : A - \Gamma'', x : A)$$

From definitions 1 and 4, we know that on the left hand side we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma + \Gamma', x : A) - \Gamma'', x : A &= (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : A - \Gamma'', x : A \\ &= \Gamma, \Gamma' - \Gamma'' \end{aligned}$$

and on the right hand side:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma + (\Gamma', x : A - \Gamma'', x : A) &= \Gamma + (\Gamma' - \Gamma'') \\ &= \Gamma, \Gamma' - \Gamma'' \end{aligned}$$

making both the left and right hand sides equivalent:

$$\Gamma, \Gamma' - \Gamma'' = \Gamma, \Gamma' - \Gamma''$$

4. $\Gamma' = \Gamma', x : [A]_r$ and $\Gamma'' = \emptyset$

We have

$$(\Gamma + \Gamma', x : [A]_r) - \emptyset = \Gamma + (x : [A]_r - \emptyset)$$

From definitions 1 and 4, we know that on the left hand side we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma + \Gamma', x : [A]_r) - \emptyset &= (\Gamma + \Gamma', x : [A]_r) \\ &= (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : [A]_r \end{aligned}$$

and on the right hand side:

$$\Gamma + (\Gamma', x : [A]_r - \emptyset) = \Gamma + (\Gamma', x : [A]_r) = (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : [A]_r$$

making both the left and right hand sides equivalent:

$$(\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : [A]_r = (\Gamma, \Gamma'), x : [A]_r$$

5. $\Gamma' = \Gamma', x : [A]_r$ and $\Gamma'' = \Gamma'', x : [A]_s$

Thus we have (for the LHS of the inequality term):

$$\Gamma + (\Gamma', x : [A]_r - \Gamma'', x : [A]_s)$$

which by context subtraction yields:

$$\Gamma + (\Gamma', x : [A]_r - \Gamma'', x : [A]_s) = \Gamma + (\Gamma' - \Gamma''), x : [A]_{q'}$$

where:

$$\exists q'.r \sqsupseteq q' + s \quad \forall \hat{q}.r \sqsupseteq \hat{q} + s \implies q' \sqsupseteq \hat{q} \quad (2)$$

And for the LHS of the inequality, from definitions 1 and 4 we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma + \Gamma', x : [A]_r) - \Gamma'', x : [A]_s &= (\Gamma + \Gamma'), x : [A]_r - \Gamma'', x : [A]_s \\ &= ((\Gamma + \Gamma') - \Gamma''), x : [A]_r - x : [A]_s \\ &= ((\Gamma + \Gamma') - \Gamma''), x : [A]_q \end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\exists q.r \sqsupseteq q + s \quad \forall \hat{q}.r \sqsupseteq \hat{q} + s \implies q \sqsupseteq \hat{q} \quad (1)$$

Applying $\exists q.r \sqsupseteq q + s$ to maximality (2) (at $\hat{q} = q$) then yields that $q \sqsubseteq q'$. Therefore, applying induction, we derive:

$$\frac{(\Gamma + (\Gamma' - \Gamma'')) \sqsubseteq ((\Gamma + \Gamma') - \Gamma'') \quad q \sqsubseteq q'}{(\Gamma + (\Gamma' - \Gamma'')), x : [A]_q \sqsubseteq ((\Gamma + \Gamma') - \Gamma''), x : [A]_{q'}}$$

satisfying the lemma statement.

Lemma 6 $((\Gamma - \Gamma') + \Gamma' \sqsubseteq \Gamma)$.

Proof. The proof follows by induction over the structure of Γ' . The possible forms of Γ' are considered in turn:

1. $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

We have:

$$(\Gamma - \emptyset) + \emptyset = \Gamma$$

From definition 4, we know that:

$$\Gamma - \emptyset = \Gamma$$

and from definition 1, we know:

$$\Gamma + \emptyset = \Gamma$$

giving us:

$$\Gamma = \Gamma$$

2. $\Gamma' = \Gamma'', x : A$

and let $\Gamma = \Gamma', x : A$.

$$(\Gamma', x : A - \Gamma'', x : A) + \Gamma'', x : A = \Gamma$$

From definition 1, we know that:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Gamma', x : A - \Gamma'', x : A) + \Gamma'', x : A &= ((\Gamma' - \Gamma'') + \Gamma''), x : A \\ \text{induction} &= \Gamma', x : A \\ &= \Gamma \end{aligned}$$

thus satisfying the lemma statement by equality.

3. $\Gamma' = \Gamma'', x : [A]_r$

and let $\Gamma = \Gamma', x : [A]_s$.

We have:

$$(\Gamma', x : [A]_s - \Gamma'', x : [A]_r) + \Gamma'', x : [A]_r$$

From definition 4, we know that:

$$\begin{aligned} &(\Gamma', x : [A]_s - \Gamma'', x : [A]_r) + \Gamma'', x : [A]_r \\ &= (\Gamma' - \Gamma''), x : [A]_q + \Gamma'', x : [A]_r \\ &= ((\Gamma' - \Gamma'') + \Gamma''), x : [A]_{q+r} \end{aligned}$$

where $s \supseteq q + r$ and $\forall q'. s \supseteq q' + r \implies q \supseteq q'$.

Then by induction we derive the ordering:

$$\frac{((\Gamma' - \Gamma'') + \Gamma'') \sqsubseteq \Gamma' \quad q + r \sqsubseteq s}{((\Gamma' - \Gamma'') + \Gamma''), x : [A]_{q+r} \sqsubseteq \Gamma', x : [A]_s}$$

which satisfies the lemma statement.

Lemma 7 (Context negation). *For all contexts Γ :*

$$\emptyset \sqsubseteq \Gamma - \Gamma$$

Proof. By induction on the structure of Γ :

- $\Gamma = \emptyset$ Trivial.
- $\Gamma = \Gamma', x : A$ then $(\Gamma', x : A) - (\Gamma', x : A) = \Gamma' - \Gamma'$ so proceed by induction.
- $\Gamma = \Gamma', x : [A]_r$ then $\exists q. (\Gamma', x : [A]_r) - (\Gamma', x : [A]_r) = (\Gamma' - \Gamma'), x : [A]_q$ such that $r \supseteq q + r$ and $\forall q'. r \supseteq q' + r \implies q \supseteq q'$.

Instantiating maximality with $q' = 0$ and reflexivity then we have $0 \sqsubseteq q$.

From this, and the inductive hypothesis, we can construct:

$$\frac{\emptyset \sqsubseteq (\Gamma' - \Gamma') \quad 0 \sqsubseteq q}{\emptyset \sqsubseteq (\Gamma' - \Gamma'), x : [A]_q}$$

Lemma 8. For all contexts Γ_1, Γ_2 , where $[\Gamma_2]$ (i.e., Γ_2 is all graded) then:

$$\Gamma_2 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_1 - (\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_2)$$

Proof. By induction on the structure of Γ_2 .

$$- \Gamma_2 = \emptyset$$

Then $\Gamma_1 - (\Gamma_1 - \emptyset) = \Gamma_1 - \Gamma_1$.

By Lemma 7, then $\emptyset \sqsubseteq (\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_1)$ satisfying this case.

$$- \Gamma_2 = \Gamma'_2, x : [A]_s$$

By the premises $\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2$ then we can assume $x \in \Gamma_1$ and thus (by context rearrangement) $\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r$.

Thus we consider $(\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r) - ((\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r) - (\Gamma'_2, x : [A]_s))$.

$$\begin{aligned} & (\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r) - ((\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r) - (\Gamma'_2, x : [A]_s)) \\ &= (\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_r) - ((\Gamma'_1 - \Gamma'_2), x : [A]_q) \\ &= (\Gamma'_1 - (\Gamma'_1 - \Gamma'_2)), x : [A]_{q'} \end{aligned}$$

where (1) $\exists q. r \sqsupseteq q + s$ with (2) $(\forall \hat{q}. r \sqsupseteq \hat{q} + s \implies q \sqsupseteq \hat{q})$
and (3) $\exists q'. r \sqsupseteq q' + q$ with (4) $(\forall \hat{q}'. r \sqsupseteq \hat{q}' + s \implies q' \sqsupseteq \hat{q}')$.

Apply (1) to (4) by letting $q' = s$ and by commutativity of $+$ then we get that $q' \sqsupseteq s$.

By induction we have that

$$\Gamma'_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma'_1 - (\Gamma'_1 - \Gamma'_2) \tag{ih}$$

Thus we get that:

$$\frac{s \sqsubseteq q' \quad \Gamma'_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma'_1 - (\Gamma'_1 - \Gamma'_2)}{\Gamma'_1, x : [A]_s \sqsubseteq (\Gamma'_1 - (\Gamma'_1 - \Gamma'_2)), x : [A]_{q'}}$$

$$- \Gamma_2 = \Gamma'_2, x : A \text{ Trivial as it violates the grading condition of the premise.}$$

Lemma 2 (Subtractive synthesis soundness). For all Γ and A then:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : A$$

i.e. t has type A under context $\Gamma - \Delta$, that contains just those linear and graded variables with grades reflecting their use in t . Appendix E provides the proof.

Proof. Structural induction over the synthesis rules. Each of the possible synthesis rules are considered in turn.

1. Case LINVAR^-

In the case of linear variable synthesis, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma} \text{LINVAR}^-$$

By the definition of context subtraction, $(\Gamma, x : A) - \Gamma = x : A$, thus we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR}$$

2. Case GRVAR^-

Matching the form of the lemma, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma, x : [A]_s} \text{GRVAR}^-$$

By the definition of context subtraction, $(\Gamma, x : [A]_r) - (\Gamma, x : [A]_s) = x : [A]_q$ where (1) $\exists q. r \sqsupseteq q + s$ and $\forall q'. r \sqsupseteq q' + s \implies q \sqsupseteq q'$.

Applying maximality (1) with $q = 1$ then we have that $1 \sqsubseteq q$ (*)

Thus, from this we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR}}{x : [A]_1 \vdash x : A} \text{DER}}{x : [A]_q \vdash x : A} \text{APPROX}}{1 \sqsubseteq q (*)}$$

3. Case $\text{R}\multimap^-$

We thus have the derivation:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^- \lambda x. t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^-$$

By induction we then have that:

$$(\Gamma, x : A) - \Delta \vdash t : B$$

Since $x \notin |\Delta|$ then by the definition of context subtraction we have that $(\Gamma, x : A) - \Delta = (\Gamma - \Delta), x : A$. From this, we can construct the following derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : A \vdash t : B}{\Gamma - \Delta \vdash \lambda x. t : A \multimap B} \text{ABS}$$

4. Case $\text{L}\multimap^-$

Matching the form of the lemma, the application derivation is:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; \Delta_2} \text{L}\multimap^-$$

By induction, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, x_2 : B) - \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : C \tag{ih1}$$

$$\Delta_1 - \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A \tag{ih2}$$

By the definition of context subtraction and since $x_2 \notin |\Delta_1|$ then (ih1) is equal to:

$$(\Gamma - \Delta_1), x_2 : B \vdash t_1 : C \quad (\text{ih1}')$$

We can thus construct the following typing derivation, making use of the admissibility of linear substitution (Lemma 1):

$$\frac{\frac{(\Gamma - \Delta_1), x_2 : B \multimap C \vdash t_1 : C}{\Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash \lambda x_2. t_1 : B \multimap C} \text{ABS} \quad \frac{\frac{\frac{}{x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta_1 - \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A}{\Delta_1 - \Delta_2, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 t_2 : B} \text{APP}}{(\Gamma - \Delta_1) + (\Delta_1 - \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash [(x_1 t_2)/x_2] t_1 : C} \text{APP}}{(\Gamma - \Delta_1), x_2 : B \multimap C \vdash t_1 : C} \text{ABS}$$

From Lemma 5, we have that

$$((\Gamma - \Delta_1) + (\Delta_1 - \Delta_2)), x_1 : A \multimap B \sqsubseteq (((\Gamma - \Delta_1) + \Delta_1) - \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B$$

and from Lemma 6, that:

$$(((\Gamma - \Delta_1) + \Delta_1) - \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B \sqsubseteq (\Gamma - \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B$$

which, since x_1 is not in Δ_2 (as x_1 is not in Γ) $(\Gamma - \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B = (\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B) - \Delta_2$. Applying these inequalities with APPROX then yields the lemma's conclusion $(\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B) - \Delta_2 \vdash [(x_1 t_2)/x_2] t_1 : C$.

5. Case $R\Box^-$

The synthesis rule for boxing can be constructed as:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^- [t]; \Gamma - r * (\Gamma - \Delta)} R\Box^-$$

By induction on the premise we get:

$$\Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : A$$

Since we apply scalar multiplication in the conclusion of the rule to $\Gamma - \Delta$ then we know that all of $\Gamma - \Delta$ must be graded assumptions.

From this, we can construct the typing derivation:

$$\frac{[\Gamma - \Delta] \vdash t : A}{r * [\Gamma - \Delta] \vdash [t] : \Box_r A} \text{PR}$$

Via Lemma 8, we then have that $(r * \Gamma - \Delta) \sqsubseteq (\Gamma - (\Gamma - (r * (\Gamma - \Delta))))$ thus, we can derived:

$$\frac{\frac{[\Gamma - \Delta] \vdash t : A}{r * [\Gamma - \Delta] \vdash [t] : \Box_r A} \text{PR} \quad \text{Lem. 8}}{\Gamma - (\Gamma - (r * (\Gamma - \Delta))) \vdash [t] : \Box_r A} \text{APPROX}$$

Satisfying the goal of the lemma.

6. Case $L\Box^-$

The synthesis rule for unboxing has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma, x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} L\Box^-$$

By induction on the premise we have that:

$$(\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r) - (\Delta, x_2 : [A]_s) \vdash t : B$$

By the definition of context subtraction we get that $\exists q$ and:

$$(\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r) - (\Delta, x_2 : [A]_s) = (\Gamma - \Delta), x_2 : [A]_q$$

such that $r = q + s$

We also have that $0 \sqsubseteq s$.

By monotonicity with $q \sqsubseteq q$ (reflexivity) and $0 \sqsubseteq s$ then $q \sqsubseteq q + s$.

By context subtraction we have $r = q + s$ therefore $q \sqsubseteq r$ (*).

From this, we can construct the typing derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash x_1 : \Box_r A \quad \text{VAR} \quad \frac{(\Gamma - \Delta), x_2 : [A]_q \vdash t : B \quad (*)}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x_2 : [A]_r \vdash t : B} \text{APPROX}}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t : B} \text{LET}}$$

Which matches the goal.

7. Case $R\otimes^-$

The synthesis rule for pair introduction has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^- \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_2} R\otimes^-$$

By induction we get:

$$\Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \tag{ih1}$$

$$\Delta_1 - \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B \tag{ih2}$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation:

$$\frac{\Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad \Delta_1 - \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B}{(\Gamma - \Delta_1) + (\Delta_1 - \Delta_2) \vdash \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle : A \otimes B} \text{PAIR}$$

From Lemma 5, we have that:

$$(\Gamma - \Delta_1) + (\Delta_1 - \Delta_2) \sqsubseteq ((\Gamma - \Delta_1) + \Delta_1) - \Delta_2$$

and from Lemma 6, that:

$$((\Gamma - \Delta_1) + \Delta_1) - \Delta_2 \sqsubseteq \Gamma - \Delta_2$$

From which we then apply APPROX to the above derivation, yielding the goal $\Gamma - \Delta_2 \vdash \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle : A \otimes B$.

8. Case L_{\otimes}^-

The synthesis rule for pair elimination has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta \quad x_1 \notin |\Delta| \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta} L_{\otimes}^-$$

By induction we get:

$$(\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B) - \Delta \vdash t_2 : C$$

since $x_1 \notin |\Delta| \wedge x_2 \notin |\Delta|$ then $(\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B) - \Delta = (\Gamma - \Delta), x_1 : A, x_2 : B$. From this, we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\overline{x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash x_3 : A \otimes B}^{\text{VAR}} \quad (\Gamma - \Delta), x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash t_2 : C}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2 : C} \text{CASE}$$

which matches the conclusion since $(\Gamma - \Delta), x_3 : A \otimes B = (\Gamma, x_3 : A \otimes B) - \Delta$ since $x_3 \notin |\Delta|$ by its disjointness from Γ .

9. Case $R_{\oplus_1}^-$ and $R_{\oplus_2}^-$

The synthesis rules for sum introduction are straightforward. For $R_{\oplus_1}^-$ we have the rule:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta}$$

By induction we have:

$$\Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : A \tag{ih1}$$

from which we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : A}{\Gamma - \Delta \vdash \mathbf{inl} t : A \oplus B} R_{\oplus_1}^-$$

Matching the goal. And likewise for $R_{\oplus_2}^-$.

10. Case L_{\oplus}^- The synthesis rule for sum elimination has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma, x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad x_3 \notin |\Delta_2|}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{case} x_1 \mathbf{of inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 | \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; \Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2} L_{\oplus}^-$$

By induction:

$$(\Gamma, x_2 : A) - \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : C \tag{ih}$$

$$(\Gamma, x_3 : B) - \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : C \tag{ih}$$

From this we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\overline{x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash t_1 : A \oplus B}^{\text{VAR}} \quad (\Gamma - \Delta_1), x_2 : A \vdash t_2 : C \quad (\Gamma - \Delta_2), x_3 : B \vdash t_3 : C}{(\Gamma, x_1 : A \oplus B) - (\Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2) \vdash \mathbf{case} t_1 \mathbf{of inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_2 | \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_3 : C} \text{CASE}$$

11. Case $R1^-$

$$\overline{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^- (); \Gamma} \text{ R1}^-$$

By Lemma 7 we have that $\emptyset \sqsubseteq \Gamma - \Gamma$ then we have:

$$\frac{\overline{\emptyset \vdash () : 1} \text{ 1}}{\Gamma - \Gamma \vdash () : 1} \text{ APPROX}$$

Matching the goal

12. Case $L1^-$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} \text{ L1}^-$$

By induction we have:

$$\Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : C \quad (\text{ih})$$

Then we make the derivation:

$$\frac{\overline{x : 1 \vdash x : 1} \text{ VAR} \quad \Gamma - \Delta \vdash t : C}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : 1 \vdash \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t : C} \text{ LET1}$$

where the context is equal to $(\Gamma, x : 1) - \Delta$.

13. Case DER^-

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad y \notin |\Delta| \quad \exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- [x/y]t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'}} \text{ DER}^-$$

By induction:

$$(\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A) - (\Delta, x : [A]_{s'}) \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

By the definition of context subtraction we have (since also $y \notin |\Delta|$)

$$\begin{aligned} & (\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A) - (\Delta, x : [A]_{s'}) \\ & = (\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_q, y : A \end{aligned}$$

where $\exists q. s \sqsupseteq q + s'$ (1) and $\forall \hat{q}. s \sqsupseteq \hat{q} + s' \implies q \sqsupseteq \hat{q}$ (2)

The goal context is computed by:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\Gamma, x : [A]_r) - (\Delta, x : [A]_{s'}) \\ & = (\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_{q'} \end{aligned}$$

where $r \sqsupseteq q' + s'$ (3) and $\forall \hat{q}'. r \sqsupseteq \hat{q}' + s' \implies q' \sqsupseteq \hat{q}'$ (4)
From the premise of DER^- we have $r \sqsupseteq (s + 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{congruence of } + \text{ and (1)} \implies s + 1 \sqsupseteq q + s' + 1 \quad (5) \\ & \text{transitivity with } \text{DER}^- \text{ premise and (5)} \implies r \sqsupseteq q + s' + 1 \quad (6) \\ & \quad + \text{ assoc./comm. on (6)} \implies r \sqsupseteq q + 1 + s' \quad (7) \\ & \text{apply (8) to (4) with } \hat{q}' = q + 1 \implies q' \sqsupseteq q + 1 \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Using this last result we derive:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_q, y : A \vdash t : B}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_q, y : [A]_1 \vdash t : B} \text{DER}}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_{q+1} \vdash [x/y]t : B} \text{CONTRACTION} \quad (8)}{(\Gamma - \Delta), x : [A]_{q'} \vdash [x/y]t : B} \text{APPROX}$$

Which matches the goal.

Lemma 3 (Additive synthesis soundness). *For all Γ and A :*

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \implies \Delta \vdash t : A$$

Appendix E provides the proof.

Proof. 1. Case LINVAR^+

In the case of linear variable synthesis, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : A} \text{LINVAR}^+$$

Therefore we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR}$$

2. Case GRVAR^+

Matching the form of the lemma, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : [A]_1} \text{GRVAR}^+$$

From this we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR}}{x : [A]_1 \vdash x : A} \text{DER}$$

3. Case $R\multimap^+$

We thus have the derivation:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A}{\Gamma \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^+ \lambda x.t; \Delta} R\multimap^+$$

By induction on the premise we then have:

$$\Delta, x : A \vdash t : B$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Delta, x : A \vdash t : B}{\Delta \vdash \lambda x.t : A \multimap B} \text{ABS}$$

4. Case $L\multimap^+$

Matching the form of the lemma, the application derivation can be constructed as:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L\multimap^+$$

By induction on the premises we then have the following typing judgments:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1, x_2 : B \vdash t_1 : C \\ \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A \end{aligned}$$

We can thus construct the following typing derivation, making use of the admissibility of linear substitution (Lemma 1):

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A}{\Delta_2, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 t_2 : B} \text{APP} \quad \Delta_1, x_2 : B \vdash t_1 : C}{(\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 : C} \text{(L. 1)}$$

5. Case $R\Box^+$

The synthesis rule for boxing can be constructed as:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^+ [t]; r * \Delta} R\Box^+$$

By induction we then have:

$$\Delta \vdash t : A$$

In the conclusion of the above derivation we know that $r * \Delta$ is defined, therefore it must be that all of Δ are graded assumptions, i.e., we have that $[\Delta]$ holds. We can thus construct the following typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{[\Delta] \vdash t : A}{r * [\Delta] \vdash [t] : \Box_r A} \text{PR}$$

6. Case DER⁺

From the dereliction rule we have:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, y : A}{\Gamma, x : [A]_s \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ [x/y]t; \Delta + x : [A]_1} \text{DER}^+$$

By induction we get:

$$\Delta, y : A \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

Case on $x \in \Delta$

– $x \in \Delta$, i.e., $\Delta = \Delta', x : [A]_{s'}$.

Then by admissibility of contraction we can derive:

$$\frac{\frac{\Delta', x : [A]_{s'}, y : A \vdash t : B}{\Delta', x : [A]_{s'}, y : [A]_1 \vdash t : B} \text{DER}}{(\Delta', x : [A]_{s'}) + x : [A]_1 \vdash [x/y]t : B}$$

Satisfying the lemma statement.

– $x \notin \Delta$. Then again from the admissibility of contraction, we derive the typing:

$$\frac{\frac{\Delta, y : A \vdash t : B}{\Delta, y : [A]_1 \vdash t : B} \text{DER}}{\Delta + x : [A]_1 \vdash [x/y]t : B}$$

which is well defined as $x \notin \Delta$ and gives the lemma conclusion.

7. Case L□⁺

The synthesis rule for unboxing has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{if } x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta \text{ then } s \sqsubseteq r \text{ else } 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Gamma, x_1 : \square_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; (\Delta \setminus x_2), x_1 : \square_r A} \text{L}\square^+$$

By induction we have that:

$$\Delta \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

Case on $x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta$

– $x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta$, i.e., $s \sqsubseteq r$.

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{\overline{x_1 : \square_r A \vdash x_1 : \square_r A} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash t : B}{\Delta, x_1 : \square_r A \vdash \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t : B} \text{LET}\square}$$

– $x_2 : [A]_s \notin \Delta$, i.e., $0 \sqsubseteq r$.

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{\overline{x_1 : \square_r A \vdash x_1 : \square_r A} \text{VAR} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash t : B}{\Delta, x_2 : [A]_0 \vdash t : B} \text{WEAK} \quad 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Delta, x_2 : [A]_r \vdash t : B} \text{APPROX}}{\Delta, x_1 : \square_r A \vdash \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t : B} \text{LET}\square$$

8. Case R_{\otimes}^+

The synthesis rule for pair introduction has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R_{\otimes}^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B \quad (\text{ih2})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B}{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 \vdash \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle : A \otimes B} \text{PAIR}$$

9. Case L_{\otimes}^+

The synthesis rule for pair elimination has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B}{\Gamma, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B} L_{\otimes}^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B \quad (\text{ih2})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{}{x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash x_3 : A \otimes B} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash t_2 : C}{\Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2 : C} \text{LETPAIR}}$$

10. Case $R_{\oplus_1}^+$ and $R_{\oplus_2}^+$

The synthesis rules for sum introduction are straightforward. For $R_{\oplus_1}^+$ we have the rule:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_1}^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta \vdash t : A \quad (\text{ih})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Delta \vdash t : A}{\Delta \vdash \mathbf{inl} t : A \oplus B} \text{INL}$$

Likewise, for the $R\oplus_2^+$ we have the synthesis rule:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} R\oplus_2^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Delta \vdash t : B}{\Delta \vdash \mathbf{inl} t : A \oplus B} \text{INR}$$

11. Case $L\oplus^+$

The synthesis rule for sum elimination has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad \Gamma, x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{case} x_1 \mathbf{of} \mathbf{inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mid \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B} L\oplus^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta_1, x_2 : A \vdash t_1 : C \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Delta_2, x_3 : B \vdash t_2 : C \quad (\text{ih2})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\overline{x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash x_1 : A \oplus B}^{\text{VAR}} \quad \Delta_1, x_2 : A \vdash t_1 : C \quad \Delta_2, x_3 : B \vdash t_2 : C}{(\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B \vdash \mathbf{case} x_1 \mathbf{of} \mathbf{inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mid \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2 : C} \text{CASE}$$

12. Case $R1^+$

The synthesis rule for unit introduction has the form:

$$\overline{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^+ (); \emptyset} R1^+$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\overline{\emptyset \vdash () : 1} 1$$

13. Case $L1^+$

The synthesis rule for unit elimination has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta, x : 1} L1^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta \vdash t : C \quad (\text{ih})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{}{x : 1 \vdash x : 1} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta \vdash t : C}{\Delta, x : 1 \vdash \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t : C} \text{LET1}$$

Lemma 4 (Additive pruning synthesis soundness). *For all Γ and A :*

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Delta \vdash t : A$$

Appendix E provides the proof.

Proof. The cases for the rules in the additive pruning synthesis calculus are equivalent to lemma (3), except for the cases of the $L' \multimap^+$ and $R' \otimes^+$ rules which we consider here:

1. Case $L' \multimap^+$

Matching the form of the lemma, the application derivation can be constructed as:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{[(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1}; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L' \multimap^+$$

By induction on the premises we then have the following typing judgments:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1, x_2 : B \vdash t_1 : C \\ \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A \end{aligned}$$

We can thus construct the following typing derivation, making use of the admissibility of linear substitution (Lemma 1):

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 : A \multimap B} \text{VAR} \quad \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : A}{\Delta_2, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash x_1 t_2 : B} \text{APP} \quad \Delta_1, x_2 : B \vdash t_1 : C}{(\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 : C} (\text{L. 1})$$

2. Case $R' \otimes^+$

The synthesis rule for the pruning alternative for pair introduction has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+_{\langle t_1, t_2 \rangle}; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R' \otimes^+$$

By induction on the premises we have that:

$$\Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B \quad (\text{ih2})$$

From this, we can construct the typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : A \quad \Delta_2 \vdash t_2 : B}{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 \vdash \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle : A \otimes B} \text{PAIR}$$

Lemma 9 (Soundness of focusing for subtractive synthesis). *For all contexts Γ , Ω and types A then:*

1. *Right Async* : $\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$
2. *Left Async* : $\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$
3. *Right Sync* : $\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$
4. *Left Sync* : $\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$
5. *Focus Right* : $\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$
6. *Focus Left* : $\Gamma; x : A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \implies \Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$

Proof. 1. Case 1. Right Async:

(a) Case $R\multimap^-$

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for abstraction introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \uparrow \Rightarrow^- \lambda x.t; \Delta} R\multimap^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 1 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R\multimap^-$ -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^- \lambda x.t; \Delta} R\multimap^-$$

(b) Case $R\uparrow^-$

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for transition to a left asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not right async}}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash C \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} R\uparrow^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

2. Case 2. Left Async:

(a) Case L_{\otimes}^-

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for pair elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta \quad x_1 \notin |\Delta| \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t_2; \Delta} L_{\otimes}^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the R_{\otimes}^- -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad x_1 \notin |\Delta| \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta|}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B) \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \mathbf{in} t; \Delta_2} L_{\otimes}^-$$

(b) Case L_{\oplus}^-

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for sum elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad x_3 \notin |\Delta_2|}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{case} x_2 \mathbf{of inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 | \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; \Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2} L_{\oplus}^-$$

By induction on the first and second premises, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the L_{\oplus}^- -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad (\Gamma, \Omega), x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad x_3 \notin |\Delta_2|}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B) \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{case} x_1 \mathbf{of inl} x_2 \rightarrow t_1 | \mathbf{inr} x_3 \rightarrow t_2; \Delta_1 \sqcap \Delta_2} L_{\oplus}^-$$

(c) Case $L1^-$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for unit elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} L1^-$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L1^-$ -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} L1^-$$

(d) Case $L\Box^-$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for graded modality elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : \Box_r A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} L\Box^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\Box^-$ -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x_2 : [A]_s \quad 0 \sqsubseteq s}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_1 : \Box_r A) \vdash B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; \Delta} L\Box^-$$

(e) Case DER^-

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for dereliction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : [A]_s, y : A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad y \notin |\Delta| \quad \exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^- [x/y]t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'}} DER^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the DER^- -synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'} \quad y \notin |\Delta| \quad \exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^- [x/y]t; \Delta, x : [A]_{s'}} DER^-$$

(f) Case $L\uparrow^-$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for transitioning an assumption from the focusing context Ω to the non-focusing context Γ , the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad \text{A not left async}}{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} L\uparrow^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

3. Case 3. Right Sync:

(a) Case R_{\otimes}^-

In the case of the right synchronous rule for pair introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_2} R_{\otimes}^-$$

By induction on the first and second premises, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the R_{\otimes}^- synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^- \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_2} R_{\otimes}^-$$

(b) Case $R_{\oplus_1}^-$ and $R_{\oplus_2}^-$

In the case of the right synchronous rules for sum introduction, the synthesis rules has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_1}^-$$

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_2}^-$$

By induction on the premises of these rules, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiations of the $R_{\oplus_1}^-$ and $R_{\oplus_2}^-$ rule in the non-focusing calculus, respectively:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_1}^-$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^- \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_2}^-$$

(c) Case $R1^-$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for unit introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^- (); \Gamma} R1^-$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R1^-$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, \Omega \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^- (); \Gamma} R1^-$$

(d) Case $R\Box^-$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for graded modality introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \Box_r A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Gamma - r * (\Gamma - \Delta)} R\Box^-$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 1 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R\Box^-$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^- [t]; \Gamma - r * (\Gamma - \Delta)} R\Box^-$$

(e) Case $R\Downarrow^-$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for transitioning back to an asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} R\Downarrow^-$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 1 of the lemma.

4. Case 4. Left Sync

(a) Case $L\multimap^-$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for application, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- [(x_1 \ t_2)/x_2]t_1; \Delta_2} L\multimap^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad (\text{ih1})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. By induction on the third premise, we have that:

$$\Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\multimap^-$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t_1; \Delta_1 \quad x_2 \notin |\Delta_1| \quad \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^- t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^- [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; \Delta_2} L\multimap^-$$

(b) Case LINVAR^-

In the case of the left synchronous rule for linear variable synthesis, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma} \text{LINVAR}^-$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the LINVAR^- synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma} \text{LINVAR}^-$$

(c) Case GRVAR^-

In the case of the left synchronous rule for graded variable synthesis, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma, x : [A]_s} \text{GRVAR}^-$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the GRVAR^- synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\exists s. r \sqsupseteq s + 1}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^- x; \Gamma, x : [A]_s} \text{GRVAR}^-$$

(d) Case $L\Downarrow^-$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for transitioning back to an asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : A \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad \text{A not atomic and not left sync}}{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} L\Downarrow^-$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

5. Case 5. Focus Right: focusR⁻

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a right synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Downarrow \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not atomic}}{\Gamma; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSR}^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

6. Case 6. Focus Left focusL⁻

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a left synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : A; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta} \text{FOCUSL}^-$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^- t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

Lemma 10 (Soundness of focusing for additive synthesis). *For all contexts Γ , Ω and types A then:*

- | | | |
|--|------------|---|
| 1. <i>Right Async</i> : $\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \Uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |
| 2. <i>Left Async</i> : $\Gamma; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |
| 3. <i>Right Sync</i> : $\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |
| 4. <i>Left Sync</i> : $\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |
| 5. <i>Focus Right</i> : $\Gamma; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |
| 6. <i>Focus Left</i> : $\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ | \implies | $\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$ |

Proof. 1. Case 1. Right Async:

(a) Case R \multimap ⁺

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for abstraction introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \vdash B \Uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \Uparrow \Rightarrow^+ \lambda x.t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 1 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the R \multimap ⁺ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, x : A}{\Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \multimap B \Rightarrow^+ \lambda x.t; \Delta} \text{R}\multimap^+$$

- (b) Case $R\uparrow^+$ In the case of the right asynchronous rule for transition to a left asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad C \text{ not right async}}{\Gamma; \Omega \vdash C \uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta} R\uparrow^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

2. Case 2. Left Async:

- (a) Case $L\otimes^+$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for pair elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \text{let } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \text{ in } t_2; \Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B} L\otimes^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\otimes^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_1 : A, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta, x_1 : A, x_2 : B}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_3 : A \otimes B) \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \text{let } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle = x_3 \text{ in } t_2; \Delta, x_3 : A \otimes B} L\otimes^+$$

- (b) Case $L\oplus^+$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for sum elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad \Gamma; \Omega, x_3 : B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \text{case } x_2 \text{ of inl } x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mid \text{inr } x_3 \rightarrow t_2; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B} L\oplus^+$$

By induction on the premises, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\oplus^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1, x_2 : A \quad (\Gamma, \Omega), x_3 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2, x_3 : B}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_1 : A \oplus B) \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \text{case } x_1 \text{ of inl } x_2 \rightarrow t_1 \mid \text{inr } x_3 \rightarrow t_2; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \Delta_2), x_1 : A \oplus B} L\oplus^+$$

(c) Case $L1^+$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for unit elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma; x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta, x : 1} L1^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L1^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : 1 \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} () = x \mathbf{in} t; \Delta, x : 1} L1^+$$

(d) Case $L\Box^+$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for graded modality elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \Omega, x_2 : [A]_r \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{if } x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta \text{ then } s \sqsubseteq r \text{ else } 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Gamma; \Omega, x_1 : \Box_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; (\Delta \setminus x_2), x_1 : \Box_r A} L\Box^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\Box^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(\Gamma, \Omega), x_2 : [A]_r \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{if } x_2 : [A]_s \in \Delta \text{ then } s \sqsubseteq r \text{ else } 0 \sqsubseteq r}{\Gamma, (\Omega, x_1 : \Box_r A) \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{let} [x_2] = x_1 \mathbf{in} t; (\Delta \setminus x_2), x_1 : \Box_r A} L\Box^+$$

(e) Case DER^+

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for dereliction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : [A]_s, y : A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, y : A}{\Gamma; x : [A]_s \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ [x/y]t; \Delta + x : [A]_1} DER^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta, y : A \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the DER^+ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : [A]_s, y : A \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta, y : A}{\Gamma, x : [A]_s \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ [x/y]t; \Delta + x : [A]_1} DER^+$$

(f) Case $L\uparrow^+$

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for transitioning an assumption from the focusing context Ω to the non-focusing context Γ , the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{A not left async}}{\Gamma; \Omega, x : A \uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta} L\uparrow^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

3. Case 3. Right Sync:

(a) Case $R\otimes^+$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for pair introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{\langle t_1, t_2 \rangle}; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R\otimes^+$$

By induction on the premises, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R\otimes^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t_1}; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t_2}; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+_{\langle t_1, t_2 \rangle}; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R\otimes^+$$

(b) Case $R\oplus_1^+$ and $R\oplus_2^+$

In the case of the right synchronous rules for sum introduction, the synthesis rules have the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t}; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{\mathbf{inl} t}; \Delta} R\oplus_1^+$$

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{t}; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \oplus B \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_{\mathbf{inr} t}; \Delta} R\oplus_2^+$$

By induction on the premises of the rules, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_{t}; \Delta \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+_{t}; \Delta \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiations of the $R_{\oplus_1}^+$ and addSumIntroRName synthesis rules in the non-focusing calculus, respectively:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inl} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_1}^+$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash A \oplus B \Rightarrow^+ \mathbf{inr} t; \Delta} R_{\oplus_2}^+$$

(c) Case $R1^+$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for unit introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\overline{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^+ (); \emptyset} R1^+$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R1^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\overline{\Gamma \vdash 1 \Rightarrow^+ (); \emptyset} R1^+$$

(d) Case $R\Box^+$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for graded modality introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \Box_r A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ [t]; r * \Delta} R\Box^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \tag{ih}$$

from case 1 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $R\Box^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Box_r A \Rightarrow^+ [t]; r * \Delta} R\Box^+$$

(e) Case $R\Downarrow^+$

In the case of the right synchronous rule for transitioning back to an asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} R\Downarrow^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \tag{ih}$$

from case 1 of the lemma.

4. Case 4. Left Sync

(a) Case $L\text{-}\multimap^+$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for application, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L\text{-}\multimap^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad (\text{ih1})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. By induction on the second premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $L\text{-}\multimap^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L\text{-}\multimap^+$$

(b) Case $LINVAR^+$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for linear variable synthesis, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma; x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : A} LINVAR^+$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $LINVAR^+$ in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : A} LINVAR^+$$

(c) Case $GRVAR^+$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for graded variable synthesis, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma; x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : [A]_1} GRVAR^+$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the $GRVAR^+$ synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, x : [A]_r \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ x; x : [A]_1} GRVAR^+$$

(d) Case $L\Downarrow^+$

In the case of the left synchronous rule for transitioning back to an asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : A \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{A not atomic and not left sync}}{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta} L\Downarrow^+$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

5. Case 5. Focus Right: focusR^+

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a right synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash C \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+ t; \Delta \quad \text{C not atomic}}{\Gamma; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{focusR}^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

6. Case 6. Focus Left: focusL^+

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a left synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta}{\Gamma, x : A; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta} \text{focusL}^+$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma.

Lemma 11 (Soundness of focusing for additive pruning synthesis). *For all contexts Γ , Ω and types A then:*

1. *Right Async* : $\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \Uparrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$
2. *Left Async* : $\Gamma; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$
3. *Right Sync* : $\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$
4. *Left Sync* : $\Gamma; x : A \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma, x : A \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$
5. *Focus Right* : $\Gamma; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$
6. *Focus Left* : $\Gamma, x : A; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t; \Delta$

Proof. 1. Case: 1. Right Async: The proofs for right asynchronous rules are equivalent to those of lemma (10)

2. Case 2. Left Async: The proofs for left asynchronous rules are equivalent to those of lemma (10)

3. Case 3. Right Sync: The proofs for right synchronous rules are equivalent to those of lemma (10), except for the case of the R'_{\otimes^+} rule:

(a) Case R'_{\otimes^+}

In the case of the right synchronous rule for pair introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R'_{\otimes^+}$$

By induction on the premises, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1 \quad (\text{ih1})$$

$$\Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the R'_{\otimes^+} synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1 \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash B \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma \vdash A \otimes B \Rightarrow^+ \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle; \Delta_1 + \Delta_2} R'_{\otimes^+}$$

4. Case 4. Left Sync: The proofs for left synchronous rules are equivalent to those of lemma (10), except for the case of the L'_{\multimap^+} rule:

(a) Case L'_{\multimap^+}

In the case of the left synchronous rule for application, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Gamma; x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow^+ t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma; x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L'_{\multimap^+}$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad (\text{ih1})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. By induction on the second premise, we have that:

$$\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t t_2; \Delta_2 \quad (\text{ih2})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the L'_{\multimap^+} synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_2 : B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+_t t_1; \Delta_1, x_2 : B \quad \Gamma - \Delta_1 \vdash A \Rightarrow^+_t t_2; \Delta_2}{\Gamma, x_1 : A \multimap B \vdash C \Rightarrow^+ [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1; (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2), x_1 : A \multimap B} L'_{\multimap^+}$$

5. Case 5. Right Focus: focusR^+ - The proof for right focusing rule is equivalent to that of lemma (10)
6. Case 6. Left Focus: focusL^+ - The proof for left focusing rule is equivalent to that of lemma (10)